

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI
OLIIY TA'LIM, FAN VA INNOVATSIYALAR
VAZIRLIGI

O'zbekiston
Milliy Pedagogika
Universiteti

BARQAROR HAYOT
xalqaro ijtimoiy-ma'rifat markazi

“ZAMONAVIY PSIXOLOGIYANING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI”

mavzusida xalqaro miqyosda ilmiy-amaliy anjuman materiallari

“Zamonaviy psixologiyaning dolzarb muammolari” mavzusida xalqaro miqyosda ilmiy-amaliy anjuman materiallari
660 b.

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi vaziri E.Karimova tahriri ostida chop etildi.

Bosh muharrir:

Z. Raxmanov – Nizomiy nomidagi O‘zbekiston Milliy Pedagogika Universiteti rektori v.v.b., iqtisodiyot fanlari bo‘yicha falsafa doktori (PhD).

Mas’ul muharrir:

G. Ibragimova – Pedagogika-psixologiya va inklyuziv ta’lim fakulteti dekani, pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor

Tahrir hay’ati:

N. Sh. Umarova – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor.

V. M. Karimova – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor.

Z. T. Nishanova – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor.

D. S. Karshiyeva – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor.

Nashrga tayyorlovchi:

R. Ashurov – psixologiya fanlari bo‘yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

To‘plamda keltirilgan maqolalarning mazmuni va keltirilgan statistik ma’lumotlarga mualliflar mas’ul.

Nizomiy nomidagi O‘zbekiston milliy pedagogika universiteti 2025-yil 10-noyabrda bo‘lib o‘tgan ilmiy texnik kengashda muhokama qilingan va nashrga tavsiya etilgan

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PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE LIFE POSITION OF UNORGANIZED YOUTH

Atabayeva Nargis Batirovna

Doctor of Psychology (DSc), Associate Professor

Alimjonova Durdona Yunusjon qizi

3rd year student of Psychology

National pedagogical university of Uzbekistan

Abstract: This article provides a comprehensive analysis of unorganized youth and their life positions. It highlights the significance of optimistic and pessimistic perspectives in enhancing social activity among young individuals. Special attention is given to identifying the factors that influence the self-activation of unorganized youth through their life positions.

Key words: unorganized youth, social activity, altruism, life position, active optimist, negativist, realist, passive pessimist, optimist, egoism, targeted psychological service, value, motive, morality.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada uyushmagan yoshlar va ularning hayotiy pozitsiyasi masalasi keng qamrovda tahlil qilingan. Xususan, optimistik va pessimistik qarashlarning shaxsning ijtimoiy faolligini oshirishdagi ahamiyati yoritilgan. Ayniqsa, uyushmagan yoshlarning hayotiy pozitsiyalari orqali o'zini faollashtirishiga ta'sir etuvchi omillar ochib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: uyushmagan yoshlar, ijtimoiy faollik, altruizm, hayotiy pozitsiya, faol optimist, negativist, realist, passiv pessimist, optimist, egoizm, maqsadli psixologik xizmat, qadriyat, motiv, axloq.

Аннотация: В статье всесторонне рассматривается проблема неорганизованной молодёжи и её жизненных позиций. Подчёркивается значение оптимистических и пессимистических взглядов в повышении социальной активности личности. Особое внимание уделено раскрытию факторов, влияющих на самоактивацию неорганизованной молодёжи через её жизненные позиции.

Ключевые слова: неорганизованная молодёжь, социальная активность, альтруизм, жизненная позиция, активный оптимист, негативист, реалист, пассивный пессимист, оптимист, эгоизм, адресная психологическая помощь, ценность, мотив, нравственность.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, globalization necessitates the implementation of certain measures to ensure the integration of youth into the socio-economic, scientific-educational, and political life of the country. When discussing the concept of «youth,» it is important to note that according to Article 3 of the «State Policy on Youth» of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 14, 2016, youth are legally defined as individuals aged fourteen to twenty-nine, constituting 58.8% of the population who have not reached the age of thirty [2]. In recent years, in line with the concept of «Educating Youth for the Fate of the Motherland,» the necessary legal and regulatory frameworks have been established based on the conceptual goals of nurturing the New Uzbekistan youth in creativity, knowledge, and education, with a focus on fostering values of patriotism, citizenship, resilience, and respect for national and universal values, aiming to cultivate firm beliefs and outlooks on life [1]. It should be emphasized that uninvolved youth are also present alongside those actively contributing to societal cohesion and progress. The term «uninvolved youth» refers to individuals who have not engaged in societal activities that contribute to its development. This term is formed by combining «uninvolved» with «youth.» The word «uninvolved» denotes the opposite of «involved,» meaning «not engaged, inexperienced, not united for a specific purpose,» while the term «youth» refers to «a group of people or organizations united for a common purpose» according to the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language [6]. Therefore, logically speaking, the word «uninvolved» acts as an antonym to «involved» or «unity,» signifying «not engaged, inexperienced, not united for a specific purpose.» Working with uninvolved youth and improving the system of providing social and psychological services to them is one of the pressing issues of today.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This longstanding issue of dealing with young people and their upbringing indicates a persistent challenge. For instance, according to a tale attributed to Luqman the Wise, he was asked, “Your advice is often aimed at young people, but the younger they are, the less they listen. Why is that?” To which Luqman the Wise replied: “If you soften the soil, remove the thorns from around it, cleanse it from harmful weeds, and water it at the right time, the tree will grow quickly, become fruitful, and flourish. Similarly, if a child is brought up well from a young age, instilled with good manners and ethics, they will not only bring happiness and success to themselves but also become useful and necessary individuals for society” [5].

Thus, working with and supporting young people, who are the backbone of society and the basis of development as well as progress of society, is crucial for shaping the foundation of societal development.

Researching the issues of youth, especially those who are not integrated into society, began in the 19th-20th centuries. According to I.S. Kon’s definition, when referring to the youth audience, “youth is a socio-demographic group characterized by youth traits, social status, and socio-psychological characteristics” [3]. This group plays a significant role in societal development. However, as emphasized earlier, there are also youth who are not integrated into society. According to American sociologist Talcott Parsons, the increase in the number of “alienated individuals” among young people is due to both objective and subjective factors. These factors contribute to the emergence of the “non-integrated” state among youth. For example, objective factors are related to the social environment, while subjective factors are associated with the individual psychological characteristics of young people. Thus, analyzing the factors contributing to the formation of the “non-integrated” youth group and addressing them are crucial.

In our research efforts, we aim to explain the unique aspects of subjective and objective factors related to youth characteristics. In our legal framework, individuals aged 14-30 have been highlighted as youth. Now, if we consider the psychological gradation of this youth period, it encompasses adolescence, youth, and young adulthood. These stages are significant in a person’s ontogenetic development as they come with their own transitions. These transitions have a significant impact on a person’s developmental trajectory. The most common of these transitions include:

- Aspects related to adaptation to society;
- Having a social status;
- Dynamic processes in parent-child relationships;
- Instilling values specific to a certain social-cultural stratum in youth;
- Combining forces against authoritarianism of elders

Psychological sources elaborate on these indicated states, which contribute to the distinct manifestation of “youth-related transitions” in personal development. Negative upbringing in the family, uncomfortable conditions in educational institutions lead to entry into the group of “non-integrated” individuals. Consequently, the socio-psychological characteristics of youth also contribute to their formation as a group of “non-integrated youth.” These socio-psychological characteristics include:

- Internal conflict;
- Psychological instability;
- A significant display of impatience;
- Tendency towards adopting subcultures

According to D. Martian, based on the socio-psychological characteristics of youth, it is possible to classify them into the following four groups:

We can observe that the first and third groups corresponding to these socio-psychological characteristics lead to the formation of the following layers of unorganized youth:

- Temporarily unemployed youth (those who have not developed clear professional aspirations, do not understand their suitability and abilities).
- Delinquent youth (deviant, criminal-prone individuals, those who have committed suicidal attempts, whose socio-legal competence is low).
- Socially passive youth (those whose ideas about themselves are not sufficiently evident, who have a need for self-improvement but are passive).

Overall, working with each category of non-integrated youth is important for increasing their social activity. Developing altruistic motives is crucial in enhancing the social activity of non-integrated youth. Altruism is an active behavior aimed at benefiting others without expecting a reward [4]. This concept, introduced by I. Kant, emphasizes the individual’s willingness to prioritize the interests of others, particularly society’s interests, over their own.

In conclusion, developing altruistic motives is essential in enhancing the social activity of non-integrated youth. By achieving altruistic motives in youth, aligning their interests with societal benefits, and transitioning

from a “passive lifestyle” to an “actively engaged” lifestyle, they can change their orientation towards societal benefits.

RESEARCH OUTCOME

Life position of a person determines his way of life and relationship with others. For this reason, we set ourselves the task of researching the life positions of 112 unorganized youths living in Tashkent and temporarily unemployed. With this, we tried to reveal the psychological essence of the social passivity of the temporarily unemployed layer of unorganized youth. To identify the socio-psychological characteristics of unorganized youth, we selected 112 respondents and conducted a survey using the “Methodology for Studying Personal Life Positions” proposed by I.S. Shuller and A.L. Komunian, as well as the modified version by N. Vodopyanova and M. Shteyn, and the “Altruism Motivation” questionnaire by S.K. Nortova-Bochaver. The results are presented in the table below.

Table-1. Social and psychological characteristics of unorganized youth

Criteria	Low level of altruistic motives	Medium level of altruism motives	High level of altruistic motives
Realist	0,02	0,04	0,55**
Active optimist	0,12	0,56**	0,16
Passive optimist	0,42**	0,09	0,11
Negativist	0,34*	-0,02	0,03
Pessimist	0,48**	-0,04	0,15

Explanation: * $p \leq 0,05$; ** $p \leq 0,01$

According to the presented statistical analysis, it is evident that the egoistic motives of unorganized youths are apparent in their life positions. Specifically, the egoistic views of unorganized youths who are passive optimists indicate their tendency towards passivity in various situations that require decision-making or action, leading to the development of passivity in situations where conflict or decision-making is demanded. These youths tend to avoid taking responsibility. They exhibit passive positions, waiting for favorable conditions for their own benefit in life situations. Often, such youths lack a sense of social involvement, independent decision-making, and independent thinking ability. Consequently, these types of unorganized youths tend to delegate important decisions to others.

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In pessimists, there is also a high prevalence of egoistic motives, which correlates with a lower level of altruism. Individuals in this group tend to not attempt to improve their situation due to the pessimistic belief that “even if I try, I won’t be able to escape from this problem.” Notably, pessimists often tend to avoid social interactions, withdraw from eating, and even turn off their phones, wanting to be left alone in their “unemployment” situation. The most dangerous aspect is that in such individuals, an increase in suicidal tendencies is observed as a result of the transition from one stressful situation to another and, depending on the person’s position, excessive emphasis on pessimistic thoughts.

Taking into account the above research findings, it is evident that unorganized youths exhibit egoistic motives in their life positions due to their inability to align their interests with societal benefits, increasing materialism, and insufficient development of legal-social consciousness, resulting in the visibility of egoistic motives in their life positions. This situation may be attributed to the transition of youths from individualism to collectivism in their life positions.

In summary, the life positions of unorganized youths directly influence the manifestation of altruism, which is the motivational basis for their social activity. Specifically, the dominance of egoistic views in negativists, passive optimists, and pessimists inhibits their social activity, while realists and active optimists among unorganized youths demonstrate movement towards activating altruistic motives by recognizing their problems and actively seeking solutions.

CONCLUSION

Based on the above analytical data and our scientific research, we can formulate the following conclusions:

- Unorganized youths constitute a diverse layer with varying values, worldviews, attitudes, and activity levels. It has been identified that the degree of expression of altruistic motives and life positions is an important socio-psychological characteristic influencing their social activity enhancement.

- In unorganized youths, a higher prevalence of passive optimistic, negative, and pessimistic life positions correlates with a lower expression of altruistic motives, indicating a predominant presence of egoistic motives.

- Furthermore, individuals with negative or pessimistic life positions exhibit lower levels of social activity, indicating the importance of stabilizing personal characteristics and developing emotional attitudes through influencing their motivational sphere to enhance altruistic motives.

- To develop altruistic motives in unorganized youths, it is essential to establish psychological mechanisms that influence cognitive, reflexive, emotional, social, and motivational areas of character development.

In general, supporting and empowering unorganized youths today entails the refinement of psychological technologies that influence their values, activities, and empathy by enhancing altruistic motives, which is of crucial importance.

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